

Kinetic Studies on Slow Coagulation of CeO_2 Sol

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A modified form of Smoluchowski's equation on kinetics of slow coagulation, proposed by Ghosh, has been tested with CeO_2 sol. An indirect method of investigation developed by Mukherjee has been adopted. The autocatalytic nature in the coagulation-velocity curve has been found to be absent in well-dialysed CeO_2 sol even after the addition of co-ions.

Rapid rate of coagulation of colloid can be expressed by the equation deduced by Smoluchowski':

$$\Sigma n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{t}{T_c}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where n_0 = number of particles originally present, Σn = number of particles at any time t during coagulation, and $T_c = 3\eta/4kTn_0$ (η is the viscosity of the dispersion medium, k , the Boltzmann constant, and T , the absolute temperature).

For the slow rate of coagulation, the above equation has been modified to take the following form:

$$\Sigma n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{\epsilon t}{T_c}} \quad \dots \quad (1a)$$

where ϵ is the percentage of successful encounters of colloid particles leading to aggregation.

To account for the observed facts, Ghosh²⁻³ has put

$$\epsilon = \frac{K}{1 + \alpha t}$$

where K and α are constants. The slow coagulation equation then takes the form:

$$\Sigma n = \frac{n_0 (1 + \alpha t)}{(1 + \beta t)} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where α and β are constants and $\beta > \alpha$.

1. Smoluchowski, *Physikal. Z.*, 1916, 17, 557, 587; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1917, 92, 129.
2. Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 671.
3. Ghosh and Gangopadhyay, *ibid.*, 1959, 36, 811.

The corresponding equations applicable for the spectrophotometric study are:

$$D_t = D_i \frac{(1+bt)}{(1+at)} \quad \dots \quad (2a)$$

where a and b are constants, and

$$I_t = I_i \frac{(1+bt)}{(1+at)} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

In these equations D_i and D_t represent galvanometer deflections at times $t=0$ and any other time t ; similarly I_i and I_t are the intensities of transmitted light at the corresponding times.

Equations (2) and (2a) have been amply verified²⁻³ from the data of various authors. Equation (3) has also been verified by Ghosh and Bandyopadhyay⁴ on coagulation of ThO_2 sol. In the present communication equation (3) has been subjected to experimental test using data on CeO_2 sol.

EXPERIMENTAL

The spectrophotometric technique developed by Mukherjee⁵ has been adopted in this study of coagulation using a Klett-Summerson colorimeter in the measurement of transmittance at different intervals of time. A green light filter No. 54 was employed. The temperature was kept at 25° during the experiments.

Preparation of the Sol⁶.—Technical quality of ceric ammonium nitrate was recrystallised from distilled water. A 5% solution of this salt was kept in a Jena flask for two weeks when the salt was hydrolysed to furnish a concentrated ceric oxide sol. It was then dialysed against distilled water for about a month after which the sol was stored in a Jena flask for ageing. The light yellow, positively charged ceric oxide sol had a pH 3.94 and sp. conductance at $25^\circ = 1.21 \times 10^{-4}$ mhos. The concentration of the sol was 1.5% by weight.

The data recorded in Tables I, II, and III deal with the verification of equation (3), whereas Fig. 1 [a, b, and c corresponding to 0, 0.8, and 4 mM per litre of $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ with a fixed coagulant concentration $C_{\text{XNO}_3} = 6.66$ mM per litre] illustrates the effect of the addition of stabilising co-ions.

DISCUSSION

Tables I, II, and III reveal that the observed values of I_t are in good agreement with those calculated with the help of equation (3), taking suitable values for a and b . With low coagulant concentration almost linear transmission-time curve is obtained.

4. *This Journal*, 1962, 39, 309.

5. Mukherjee and Majumder, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924 125, 794.

6. Blitz, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 4431.

TABLE I

Time (t).	I_t			
	$C_{\text{KCl}} = 5\text{mM/litre.}$		$C_{\text{KNO}_3} = 5\text{mM/litre.}$	
	Obs.	Calc. $a=0.0341$ $b=0.0305$	Obs.	Calc. $a=0.02045$ $b=0.01676$
0 min.	99.3	99.3	99.3	99.3
5	97.7	97.8	97.4	97.6
10	96.4	96.6	95.5	96.2
20	95.1	95.1	93.9	94.1
30	..	..	92.5	92.5
35	93.8	93.6	..	..
45	..	..	90.8	90.7
50	93.0	92.7	..	..
60	..	..	89.5	89.4
70	92.0	92.0	..	..
80	..	..	88.2	88.2
95	91.1	91.3	..	..
105	..	..	86.7	87.1
120	90.1	90.9	..	..
145	89.7	90.6	..	..
160	..	..	85.2	85.8
175	89.2	90.3	..	..

TABLE II

Time (t).	I_t			
	$C_{\text{KCl}} = 5.88\text{ mM/litre.}$		$C_{\text{KNO}_3} = 5.88\text{ mM/litre.}$	
	Obs.	Calc. $a=0.03909$ $b=0.03047$	Obs.	Calc. $a=0.06797$ $b=0.05387$
0 min.	99.3	99.3	99.3	99.3
5	95.2	95.7	93.8	94.1
10	92.8	93.1	90.9	91.0
15	..	..	88.9	88.0
20	89.7	8.97	..	..
25	..	..	85.7	86.3
30	87.9	87.5	..	..
40	85.9	85.9	83.7	84.2
50	84.3	84.8	..	..
60	..	..	82.5	82.6
60	..	..	..	..
65	83.6	83.6	..	..
80	82.8	82.7	81.9	81.9
100	82.0	81.9	81.5	81.3
120	81.7	81.3	81.1	80.9
150	..	..	80.7	80.6

TABLE III

t.	I_t			
	$C_{KCl} = 6.66 \text{ m.M./litre.}$		$C_{KNO_3} = 6.66 \text{ m.M./litre.}$	
	Obs.	Calc. $a=0.2077$ $b=0.1043$	Obs.	Calc. $a=0.2443$ $b=0.1926$
0 mir.	90.3	90.3	90.3	90.3
2	93.1	93.3	92.4	92.4
5	96.5	96.7	97.1	96.5
10	95.3	95.3	94.4	94.4
15	93.1	93.6	92.8	92.8
25	91.2	91.9	90.9	91.2
35	..	..	90.5	90.5
40	90.4	90.6	..	..
45	..	..	79.8	80.0
60	90.1	90.1	79.6	79.6
80	79.8	79.7	79.5	79.3
100	79.7	79.5	..	..

Since the coagulating concentration of counter ions varies inversely as the sixth power of valency (vide Verwey and Overbeek⁸), the spectrophotometric way of study of coagulation becomes unsuitable when polyvalent counter ions are used to coagulate ceric oxide sol. For this reason only univalent coagulant ions have been employed. The above tables indicate that the rate of coagulation of CeO_2 sol for any concentration of KNO_3 is higher than that for the same concentration of KCl . The same observation has been made by Ghosh and Bandyopadhyay⁴.

FIG. 1

As regards the autocatalytic nature of the coagulation—velocity curve, as observed by Nabar and Prasad⁷ in their kinetic study on coagulation of CeO_2 sol, the present author

7. *This Journal*, 1933, 10, 153.

8. "Theory of the Stability of Lyophobic Colloids",

has not been able to detect the S-shape in the well-dialysed sol. The appearance of S-shape in the coagulation curve has been attributed by Nabar and Prasad⁷ to the presence of considerable amount of stabilising ion and also to the concentration of the sol itself. The addition, however, of small amount of co-ions has been found to lower the coagulation velocity only without producing any S-shape, which may be noticed from Fig. 1. It appears therefore that other factors might be responsible for causing an S-shape in the curve.

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